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**THE NEWEST ANTHTOPONYMIC TRENDS
IN FOREIGN NAME PREFERENCES, IN NAME GIVING PROCESS,
IN NORTHERN PART OF BULGARIA
(OVER THE ANTHROPOSOCIOONOMASTIC DATA FOR PLEVEN,
RUSE, VELIKO TARNOVO, AND VARNA FOR THE PERIOD 2008-2018)¹**

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Abstract

The present text aims to study the newest anthroponymic trends, and in particular, the new variants of traditional foreign given names, part of the onomasticon, in four of the most important and big settlements in Northern Bulgaria – Pleven, Veliko Tarnovo, Ruse, and Varna. Official statistical data of the National Statistical Institute (NSI) in the Republic of Bulgaria for a 10-year period (2008-2018) is used.

Keywords: *Bulgarian traditional foreign given name, new variants of traditional foreign given name, Pleven, Varna, Ruse, Veliko Tarnovo, Northern Bulgaria settlement*

Rezumat

În articol, ne propunem să studiem cele mai noi tendințe antroponimice și, în special, noile variante ale numelor tradiționale străine, care fac parte din onomasticonul a patru dintre așezările importante și mari din nordul Bulgariei – Pleven, Veliko Tarnovo, Ruse și Varna. Se utilizează datele statistice oficiale ale Institutului Național de Statistică (INS) din Republica Bulgaria pentru o perioadă de 10 ani (2008-2018).

Cuvinte-cheie: *nume bulgare venite din alte limbi; variante noi ale numelor venite din alte limbi, Plevna Varna, Ruse, Veliko Târnovo, așezare din Bulgaria de Nord*

I. Introduction

The present text is part of a bigger research on the contemporary trends in name-giving in some of the biggest Bulgarian settlements under the project “Personal Names in Bulgaria in the Beginning of the 21st Century”, developed by scholars from the Institute for Bulgarian Language, the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Onomastic Section and financed by the National Science Fund of the Republic of Bulgaria.

The focus here is on new variants of traditional Bulgarian proper nouns entering the onomasticon due to the strong influence of the so-called international names preferred by parents nowadays all over Europe.

¹The present study is conducted under the project “Personal Names in Bulgaria in the Beginning of 21st Century” with the support of the National Science Fund of the Republic of Bulgaria, Grant N^o KPI-06-H-40/10, 10 December 2019.

The research object consists of the mentioned above onyms officially registered by the National Statistical Institute (NSI) in the Republic of Bulgaria for a 10-year period (2008-2018) in the biggest towns in North Bulgaria, Pleven, Ruse, Veliko Tarnovo, and Varna.

The main aim is their positioning in the top 15 lists with masculine and feminine proper nouns to be followed and compared with the traditional forms of the same foreign anthroponyms.

Part of the investigation are only the names with 3 and more references in the official statistical data in accordance with the personal data protection and the Law on Statistics of the Republic of Bulgaria (Vlahova-Angelova, 2021, p. 187) and that is the reason why there are some gaps in the chart tables.

It is important to mention that it is obvious that in many cases a given name included in the table has the same frequency of usage as others. Due to it, the top 15 list does not contain every forename recorded and a phenomenon is observed that all the forenames officially registered are part of the chart, with the exception of those with a single or dual reference.

The new variants of traditional foreign anthroponyms, which are the object of the present research, are given in bold in the tables below.

The methodology used is developed by Anna Choleva-Dimitrova and Boryan Yanev and presented in their work of 2015 entitled “Съвременната българска антропонимна система (мода на личните имена)”, ч. 1. It is a “corpus-based empirical study” on the NSI official data (Choleva-Dimitrova & Dancheva, 2018, p. 122).

II. Pleven Given Name Data Analysis

There are 1088 children born in Pleven in 2008 (537 boys and 551 girls). In 2014, their number is 797 (423 boys and 374 girls), while for 2018 it is 725 (355 boys and 370 girls).

1. Masculine Given Names

Position	Years, Names and Number of References (...)		
	2008	2014	2018
1.	Георги/Georgi (25)	Александър/ Aleksandar, Мартин/Martin (20)	Александър/ Aleksandar, Никола/Nikola (15)
2.	Мартин/Martin (23)	Георги/Georgi (17)	Борис/Boris, Мартин/Martin, Теодор/Teodor (13)
3.	Александър/ Aleksandar (20)	Виктор/Viktor, Даниел/Daniel, Никола/Nikola,	Виктор/Viktor, Даниел/Daniel, Кристиян/Kristiyan

		<i>Теодор/Teodor</i> (12)	(12)
4.	Виктор/Viktor (19)	Калоян/Kaloyan, <i>Кристиан/Kristiyan</i> (11)	Божидар/Bozhidar, Георги/Georgi (10)
5.	Николай/ Nikolay (171)	Владислав/Vladislav, Иван/Ivan (9)	Калоян/Kaloyan, Симеон/Simeon (9)
6.	<i>Теодор/Teodor</i> (15)	Ивайло/Ivaylo, Михаил/Mihail, Николай/Nikolay, Преслав/Preslav (8)	Андрей/Andrey (7)
7.	Даниел/Daniel (12)	Божидар/Bozhidar, Борис/Boris, Борислав/Borislav, Владимир/Vladimir, Габриел/Gabriel, Симеон/Simeon (7)	Владимир/Vladimir, Самуил/Samuil, Стефан/Stefan (6)
8.	<i>Кристиан/Kristiyan</i> (11)	<i>Кристиан/Kristiyan</i> , Христиан/Hristiyan (6)	Валентин/Valentin, Иван/Ivan, Николай/Nikolay, Станислав/Stanislav (5)
9.	Денислав/ Denislav, Иван/Ivan, <i>Кристиан/Kristian</i> (10)	Алекс/Aleks, Димитър/Dimitar, Йоан/Yoan, Радослав/Radoslav, Самуил/Samuil (5)	Борислав/Borislav, Велизар/Velizar Владислав/Vladislav, Ивайло/Ivaylo, Михаил/Mihail, Пламен/Plamen, Преслав/Preslav, Радослав/Radoslav (4)
10.	Борис/Boris, Димитър/ Dimitar, Христиан/ Hristiyan, Цветомир/ Tzvetomir (9)	Васил/Vasil, Максим/Maksim, Момчил/Momchil, Петър/Petar (4)	<i>Антонио/Antonio</i> , Габриел/Gabriel, Димитър/Dimitar, <i>Константин/ Konstantin</i> , Петър/Petar (3)
11.	Алекс/Aleks, Божидар/ Bozhidar, Валентин/	Валентин/Valentin, Велин/Velin, Велислав/Velislav, Галин/Galin,	-

	Valentin, Габриел/ Gabriel, Никола/Nikola, Петър/Petar (8)	Давид/David, Дарин/Darin, Ивелин/Ivelin, Камен/Kamen, Лъчезар/Lachezar, Станислав/Stanislav (3)	
12.	Ивайло/Ivaylo, Радослав/ Radoslav, Станислав/ Stanislav (6)	-	-
13.	Ангел/Angel, Боян/Boyan, Лъчезар/ Lachezar, Мирослав/ Miroslav, Павел/Pavel, Преслав/Preslav, Стефан/Stefan (5)	-	-
14.	Борислав/ Borislav, Велислав/ Velislav, Давид/David, Емил/Emil, Ивелин/Ivelin, Илиян/Iliyan, Йоан/Yoan, Калоян/Kaloyan, Марио/Mario, Пламен/Plamen, Цветан/Tzvetan (4)	-	-
15.	Андрей/Andrey, Венелин/Venelin, Владислав/ Vladislav, Денис/Denis, Деян/Deyan, Здравко/ Zdravko, Калин/Kalin,	-	-

	Константин/ <i>Konstantin</i> , Любомир/ <i>Lyubomir</i> , Милен/ <i>Milen</i> , Момчил/ <i>Momchil</i> , Росен/ <i>Rosen</i> , Светлин/ <i>Svetlin</i> , Светослав/ <i>Svetoslav</i> , Симеон/ <i>Simeon</i> , Стилян/ <i>Stilyan</i> , Христо/ <i>Hristo</i> (3)		
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Table 1: List of Top 15 Masculine Given Names in Pleven, 2008-2018

For 2008 the new male anthroponyms that represent new variants of traditional foreign proper names are:

- Теодор/*Teodor* (6th position, 15 references; variant of *Тодор/Todor*);
- Крестиян/*Kristiyan* (8th position, 11 references, variant of *Християн/Hristiyan*);
- Крестиан/*Kristian* (9th position, 10 references, variant of *Хрестиан/Hristian*);
- Марио/*Mario* (14th position, 4 references, variant of *Марин/Marin*);
- Константин/*Konstantin* (15th position, 3 references, variant of *Костадин/Kostadin*).

For 2014 their number is less but they took higher positions in the chart:

- Теодор/*Teodor* (3rd position, 12 references);
- Крестиян/*Kristiyan* (4th position, 11 references);
- Крестиан/*Kristiyan* (8th position, 6 references).

For 2018 the position of *Теодор/Teodor* (2nd position, 13 references), and *Крестиян/Kristiyan* (3rd position, 12 references) is even higher if compared with the 2014 data. *Константин/Konstantin* (10th position, 3 references) appeared again, as well as *Антонио/Antonio* (10th position with 3 references, variant of *Антон/Anton*), recorded for the first time.

2. Feminine Given Names

Position	Years, Names and Number of References (...)		
	2008	2014	2018
1.	Виктория/ <i>Viktoriya</i> (25)	<i>Никол/Nikol</i> (19)	Виктория/ <i>Viktoriya</i> (16)
2.	Александра/ <i>Aleksandra</i> (17)	Виктория/ <i>Viktoriya</i> (17)	<i>Никол/Nikol</i> (14)

3.	Мария/Mariya (15)	Габриела/Gabriela, Дария/Dariya (10)	Александра/ Aleksandra, Рая/Raya (12)
4.	<i>Никол/Nikol</i> (14)	Йоана/Yoana (9)	София/Sofiya (11)
5.	Симона/Simona (12)	Ивайла/Ivayla, Мария/Mariya (8)	Михаела/Mihaela (9)
6.	Габриела/Gabriela (11)	Калина/Kalina (7)	Йоана/Yoana (7)
7.	Ванеса/Vanesa, Михаела/Mihaela, Преслава/Preslava (10)	Елена/Elena, Моника/Monika (6)	Габриела/Gabriela, Карина/Karina, Катерина/Katerina, Кристина/Kristina (6)
8.	Гергана/Gergana, Йоана/Yoana, Марина/Marina (9)	Александра/ Aleksandra, Даниела/Daniela, <i>Даяна/Dayana,</i> Крисиya/Krisiya, Лора/Lora, <i>Теодора/Teodora</i> (5)	Ванеса/Vanesa, Ема/Ema, Йоанна/Yoanna, Моника/Monika, Симона/Simona (5)
9.	Моника/Monika, Рая/Raya, <i>Теодора/Teodora</i> (8)	Валентина/ Valentina, Ванеса/Vanesa, Гергана/Gergana, Десислава/ Desislava, Ева/Eva, Елица/Elitza, Карина/Karina, Мартина/Martina, Михаела/Mihaela, Пламена/Plamena, Преслава/Preslava, Симона/Simona, София/Sofiya (4)	Белослава/ Beloslava, Борислава/ Borislava, Вяра/Vyara, Даная/Danaya, Елена/Elena, Ивайла/Ivayla, Преслава/Preslava, <i>Стефани/Stefani</i> (4)
10.	Андреа/Andrea, Елена/Elena, Красимира/Krasimira, <i>Кристина/Kristina</i> (7)	Аделина/Adelina, Божидара/ Bozhidara, Дара/Dara, Диана/Diana, Ивон/Ivon,	Анелия/Aneliya, Анна/Anna, Божидара/ Bozhidara, Ваяна/Vayana, Гергана/Gergana,

		Магдалена/ Magdalena, Мирела/Mirela, Радост/Radost, Ралица/Ralitzа, Рая/Raya, Сияна/Siyana, Яна/Yana (3)	Дария/Dariya, Даяна/Dayana, Зара/Zara, Ивана/Ivana, Калина/Kalina, Кристиана/ Kristiana, Лора/Lora, Магдалена/ Magdalena, Марина/Marina, Натали/Natali, Пламена/Plamena, Теодора/Teodora, Яна/Yana (3)
11.	Деница/Denitza, Ева/Eva, Ивайла/Ivayla, Ивана/Ivana, Стефани/Stefani (6)	-	-
12.	Борислава/Borislava, Десислава/Desislava, Емилия/Emiliya, Зорница/Zornitza, Калина/Kalina, Магдалена/Magdalena, Пламена/Plamena, Сияна/Siyana (5)	-	-
13.	Даная/Danaya, Дария/Dariya, Кристияна/Kristiyana, Марина/Marina, Ралица/Ralitzа, Христина/Hristina, Цветелина/Tzvetelina, Цветина/Tzvetina (4)	-	-
14.	Валентина/Valentina, Василена/Vasilena, Джулия/Dzhuliya, Ива/Iva, Ивелина/Ivelina, Катерина/Katerina, Мая/Maya,	-	-

	<i>Натали/Natali,</i> <i>Наталия/Nataliya,</i> <i>Нели/Neli,</i> <i>Ния/Niya,</i> <i>Полина/Polina,</i> <i>Силвия/Silviya,</i> <i>Стела/Stela,</i> <i>Стефания/Stefaniya,</i> <i>Цветозара/Tzvetozara,</i> <i>Яна/Yana,</i> <i>Яница/Yanitza</i> (3)		
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Table 2: List of Top 15 Feminine Given Names in Pleven, 2008-2018

For 2008 the new female anthroponyms that represent new variants of traditional foreign proper names are:

- *Никол/Nikol* (4th position, 14 references, variant of *Николема/Nikoleta*);
- *Теодора/Teodora* (9th position, 8 references, variant of *Тодора/Todora*);
- *Кристина/Kristina* (10th position, 7 references, variant of *Христина/Hristina*);
- *Стефани/Stefani* (11th position, 6 references, variant of *Стефка/Stefka*);
- *Кристияна/Kristiyana* (13th position, 4 references, variant of *Християна/Hristiyana*);
- *Джулия/Dzhuliya* (14th position, 3 references, variant of *Юлия/Yuliya*);
- *Натали/Natali* (14th position, 3 references, variant of *Наталия/Nataliya*).

For 2014 their number is diminished but they are becoming more preferred *Никол/Nikol* (1st position, 19 references), *Даяна/Dayana* (8th position, 5 references, variant of *Диана/Diana*), and *Теодора/Teodora* (8th position, 5 references).

For 2018 their number is getting higher as well as their positions in the chart: *Никол/Nikol* (2nd position, 14 references), *Стефани/Stefani* (9th position, 4 references), *Даяна/Dayana*, *Кристиана/Kristiana*, *Натали/Natali*, and *Теодора/Teodora* (10th position, 3 references).

III. Ruse Given Name Data Analysis

There are 1492 children born in Ruse in 2008 (761 boys and 731 girls). In 2014, their number is 1254 (637 boys and 617 girls), while for 2018 it is 1135 (583 boys and 552 girls).

1. Masculine Given Names

Position	Years, Names and Number of References (...)		
	2008	2014	2018
1.	Александър/ Aleksandar	Никола/Nikola (27)	Даниел/Daniel (25)

	(39)		
2.	Мартин/Martin, Никола/Nikola (28)	Даниел/Daniel (26)	Александър/ Aleksandar (24)
3.	Георги/Georgi (26)	Александър/ Aleksandar, Виктор/Viktor, Калоян/Kaloyan, Теодор/Teodor (19)	Мартин/Martin (20)
4.	Виктор/Viktor (25)	Георги/Georgi (18)	Георги/Georgi (18)
5.	Кристиян/Kristiyan (21)	Мартин/Martin (16)	Борис/Boris (16)
6.	Даниел/Daniel (19)	Михаил/Mihail, Николай/Nikolay (14)	Калоян/Kaloyan (15)
7.	Алекс/Aleks, Калоян/Kaloyan, Преслав/Preslav, Теодор/Teodor (15)	Кристиян/Kristiyan (12)	Кристиян/ Kristiyan (14)
8.	Николай/Nikolay (14)	Алекс/Aleks, Ивайло/Ivaylo (10)	Виктор/Viktor, Михаил/Mihail, Никола/Nikola (13)
9.	Симеон/Simeon (13)	Борис/Boris, Денис/Denis, Максим/Maksim (9)	Симеон/Simeon (12)
10.	Боян/Boyan, Димитър/Dimitar, Иван/Ivan (12)	Борислав/Borislav (8)	Емир/Emir (10)
11.	Валентин/Valentin (11)	Йоан/Yoan, Преслав/Preslav, Симеон/Simeon (7)	Николай/Nikolay, Преслав/Preslav (9)
12.	Борислав/Borislav, Максим/Maksim (9)	Ефе/Efe, Филип/Filip (6)	Теодор/Teodor (8)
13.	Божидар/Bozhidar, Габриел/Gabriel (8)	Божидар/Bozhidar, Габриел/Gabriel, Джан/Dzhan, Иван/Ivan, Мерт/Mert,	Йоан/Yoan (7)

		Петър/Petar, Пресиян/Presiyan, Радослав/Radoslav, Самуил/Samuil (5)	
14.	Ивайло/Ivaylo, Петър/Petar, Радослав/Radoslav (7)	Андрей/Andrey, Богомил/Bogomil, Боян/Boyan, Васил/Vasil, Владимир/Vladimir, Илия/Иliya, Йордан/Yordan, Константин/ Konstantin, Кристиан/Kristian, Лъчезар/Lachezar, Мирослав/Miroslav, Онур/Onur, Павел/Pavel, Пламен/Plamen, Стефан/Stefan (4)	Алекс/Aleks, Божидар/Bozhidar, Димитър/Dimitar, Максим/Maksim, Петър/Petar (6)
15.	Борис/Boris, Михаил/Mihail (6)	Антон/Anton, Владислав/ Vladislav, Давид/David, Денислав/Denislav, Деян/Deyan, Димитър/Dimitar, Ивелин/Ivelin, Калин/Kalin, Михаел/Mihael, Румен/Rumen, Станчо/Stanchо, Христо/Hristo, Янислав/Yanislav (3)	Андрей/Andrey, Борислав/Borislav, Владислав/ Vladislav, Денис/Denis, Йордан/Yordan, Самуил/Samuil (5)

Table 3: List of Top 15 Masculine Given Names in Ruse, 2008-2018

For 2008 the new male anthroponyms that represent new variants of traditional foreign proper names are:

- *Кристиан/Kristiyan* (5th position, 21 references, variant *Християн/Hristiyan*);
- *Теодор/Teodor* (7th position, 15 references, variant of *Тодор/Todor*).

For 2014 they increased for *Теодор/Teodor* (3rd position, 19 references), *Кристиан/Kristiyan* (7th position, 12 references), *Константин/Konstantin* (14th position, 4 references, variant of *Костадин/Kostadin*), *Кристиан/ Kris-*

tian (14th position, 4 references, variant of *Християн/Hristian*), and *Михаел/Mihael* (15th position, 3 references, variant of *Михаил/Mihail*), while in 2018 they decreased for *Кристиан/Kristiyan* (7th position, 14 references) and *Теодор/Teodor* (12th position, 8 references).

2. Feminine Given Names

Position	Years, Names and Number of References (...)		
	2008	2014	2018
1.	Виктория/ Viktoriya (21)	<i>Никол/Nikol</i> (24)	Виктория/Viktoriya (22)
2.	<i>Никол/Nikol</i> (20)	Виктория/Viktoriya (22)	<i>Никол/Nikol</i> (17)
3.	Габриела/ Gabriela (17)	Мария/Mariya (12)	София/Sofiya (15)
4.	Александра/ Aleksandra, Йоана/Yoana (14)	Симона/Simona (11)	Габриела/Gabriela (12)
5.	Преслава/ Preslava, <i>Теодора/Teodora</i> (13)	Михаела/Mihaela, София/Sofiya (10)	Дария/Dariya, Симона/Simona (11)
6.	<i>Кристина/ Kristina,</i> Рая/Raya, Симона/Simona (12)	Александра/ Aleksandra (9)	<i>Теодора/Teodora</i> (10)
7.	Моника/Моника (11)	Елена/Elena, Ивайла/Ivayla, Йоана/Yoana (8)	Сияна/Siyana (9)
8.	Михаела/ Mihaela (8)	Ема/Ема, Калина/Kalina, <i>Кристина/Kristina,</i> Рая/Raya, <i>Теодора/Teodora</i> (7)	Михаела/Mihaela, Яна/Yana (8)
9.	Василена/ Vasilena, Даная/Danaya, Ева/Eva, Ива/Iva, Калина/Kalina, Мелиса/Melisa	Ванеса/Vanesa, Габриела/Gabriela, Дария/Dariya, Ева/Eva, Крися/Krisiya, Сияна/Siyana (6)	Александра/ Aleksandra, Белослава/Beloslava, Ема/Ема, Рая/Raya (7)

	(7)		
10.	Валентина/ Valentina, Гергана/ Gergana, Емилия/Emiliya, Лора/Lora, Мария/Mariya (6)	Андреа/ Andrea, Гергана/Gergana, Зара/Zara, Ивон/Ivon, Мая/Maya, Моника/Monika, Натали/Natali (5)	Елена/Elena, Марина/Marina, Мария/Mariya (6)
11.	Антония/ Antoniya, Вероника/ Veronika, Дария/Dariya, Десислава/ Desislava, Елена/Elena, Ема/Ема, Ивайла/Ivayla, Ивет/Ivet, Йоанна/Уоанна, Мартина/ Martina, Ралица/Ralitzа, Селин/Selin (5)	Ваяна/Vayana, Даная/Danaya, Даяна/Dayana, Деница/Denitza, Екатерина/Ekaterina, Елиф/Elif, Ива/Iva, Катерина/Katerina, Магдалена/ Magdalena, Мартина/Martina, Мелиса/Melisa, Преслава/Preslava (4)	Анастасия/ Anastasiya, Анна/Anna, Божидара/Bozhidara, Ванеса/Vanesa, Ивайла/Ivayla, Ивона/Ivona, Калина/Kalina, Мартина/Martina, Микаела/Mikaela, Моника/Monika, Ния/Niya, Радина/Radina (5)
12.	Анастасия/ Anastasiya, Анна/Анна, Боряна/Boryana, Ванеса/Vanesa, Даниела/ Daniela, Деница/Denitza, Елеонора/ Eleonora, Елица/Elitza, Емма/Емма, Зорница/ Zornitza, Мелек/Melek, Пламена/ Plamena, Стела/Stela, Стефани/Stefani (4)	Аделина/Adelina, Антония/Antoniya, Белослава/Beloslava, Борислава/Borislava, Дамла/Damla, Евелин/Evelin, Емилия/Emiliya, Катрин/Katrin, Кристияна/Kristiyana, Лора/Lora, Марина/Marina, Пресияна/Presiyana, Радина/Radina, Яна/Yana (3)	Мелиса/Melisa, Пресияна/Presiyana, Радост/Radost (4)

13.	Ана-Мария/ Ана-Марија, Андреа/ Andrea, Анелия/ Aneliya, Дарина/ Darina, Даяна/ Dayana, Екатерина/ Ekaterina, Елинор/ Elinor, Ивелина/ Ivelina, Ивета/ Iveta, Ивона/ Ivona, Каролина/ Karolina, Кристияна/ Kristiyana, Лилия/ Liliya, Магдалена/ Magdalena, Полина/ Polina, Сиана/ Siana, Силвена/ Silvena, Силвия/ Silviya, София/ Sofiya, Цвета/ Tzveta (3)	-	Алейна/ Aleyna, Анна-Мария/ Анна-Марија, Антония/ Antoniya, Ваяна/ Vayana, Вяра/ Vyara, Десислава/ Desislava, Екатерина/ Ekaterina, Емма/ Emma, Камелия/ Kameliya, Карина/ Karina, Катерина/ Katerina, Кристина/ Kristina, Матейа/ Mateya, Наталия/ Nataliya, Преслава/ Preslava, Силвия/ Silviya, Стела/ Stela, Стефани/ Stefani, Цветина/ Tzvetina (3)
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Table 4: List of Top 15 Feminine Given Names in Ruse, 2008-2018

For 2008 the new female anthroponyms that represent new variants of traditional foreign proper nouns names are: *Никол/ Nikol* (2nd position, 20 references, variant of *Никоleta/ Nikoleta*), *Теодора/ Teodora* (5th position, 13 references, variant of *Тодора/ Todora*), *Кристина/ Kristina* (6th position, 12 references, variant of *Христина/ Hristina*), *Стефани/ Stefani* (12th position, 4 references, variant of *Стефка/ Stefka*), *Даяна/ Dayana* (variant of *Диана/ Diana*), *Елинор/ Elinor* (variant of *Елеонора/ Eleonora*), *Кристияна/ Kristiyana* (variant of *Християна/ Hritiyana*) all of them in the 13th position with 3 references.

For 2014 the list includes: *Никол/ Nikol* (1st position, 24 references, *Кристина/ Kristina*, and *Теодора/ Teodora* (8th position, 7 references), *Натали/ Natali* (10th position, 5 references, variant of *Наталия/ Nataliya*), *Даяна/ Dayana* (11th position, 4 references), *Евелин/ Evelin* (variant of *Евелина/ Evelina*), *Катрин/ Katrin* (variant of *Катерина/ Katerina*), and *Кристияна/ Kristiyana* (12th position, 3 references).

For 2018 they are: *Никол/ Nikol* (2nd position, 17 references), *Теодора/ Teodora* (6th position, 10 references), *Микаела/ Mikaela* (11th position, 5 references,

variant of *Михаела/ Mihaela*), *Кристина/ Kristina*, and *Стефани/ Stefani* (13th position, 3 references).

IV. Veliko Tarnovo Given Name Data Analysis

In 2008, 726 children (367 boys and 359 girls) were born in Veliko Tarnovo. The number of the newly born in 2014 is 643 (330 boys and 313 girls), while in 2018 it decreased to 614 (318 boys and 296 girls).

1. Masculine Given Names

Position	2008	2014	2018
1.	Александър/ Aleksandar (23)	Мартин/Martin (18)	Мартин/Martin (18)
2.	Георги/Georgi (14)	Александър/ Aleksandar (16)	Борис/Boris (17)
3.	Ивайло/Ivaylo, Мартин/Martin (12)	Георги/Georgi (14)	Георги/Georgi (14)
4.	Калоян/Kaloyan, <i>Кристиан/ Kristian</i> (10)	Никола/Nikola (12)	Александър/ Aleksandar, Даниел/Daniel (13)
5.	Никола/Nikola (9)	Калоян/Kaloyan (11)	Никола/Nikola (12)
6.	Виктор/Viktor, Денислав/Denislav, Иван/Ivan (8)	Божидар/Vozhidar, Виктор/Viktor, Даниел/Daniel, Димитър/Dimitar, Николай/Nikolay (8)	<i>Теодор/Teodor</i> (11)
7.	Даниел/Daniel, Димитър/Dimitar, Симеон/Simeon (7)	<i>Кристиан/ Kristiyan</i> (7)	Калоян/Kaloyan (10)
8.	<i>Константин/ Konstantin</i> , <i>Кристиан/ Kristiyan</i> , Николай/Nikolay (6)	Боян/Boyan, Владимир/Vladimir, Иван/Ivan, Павел/Pavel, <i>Теодор/Teodor</i> (6)	Преслав/Preslav (8)
9.	Дамян/Damyan, Пламен/Plamen, Стефан/Stafan, <i>Теодор/Teodor</i>	Борис/Boris, Ивайло/Ivaylo (5)	Владимир/ Vladimir (7)

	(5)		
10.	Алекс/Aleks, Борис/Boris, Йоан/Yoan, Максим/Maksim, Преслав/Preslav, Християн/Hristiyan (4)	Борислав/Borislav, Валери/Valeri, Габриел/Gabriel, Денислав/Denislav, Йоан/Yoan, Мирослав/Miroslav, Стефан/Stafan (4)	Виктор/Viktor, Николай/Nikolay, Стефан/Stafan (6)
11.	Атанас/Atanas, Валентин/Valentin, Давид/David, Иво/Ivo, Кирил/Kiril, Павел/Pavel (3)	Адриан/Adrian, Веселин/Veselin, Давид/David, Максим/Maksim, Михаил/Mihail, Петко/Petko, Петър/Petar, Преслав/Preslav, Радостин/Radostin, Цветослав/Tzvetoslav (3)	Михаил/Mihail (5)
12.	-	-	Боян/Boyan, Давид/David, Ивайло/Ivaylo, Кристиан/ Kristian, Любомир/ Lyubomir, Симеон/Simeon (4)
13.	-	-	Алекс/Aleks, Алексей/Aleksey, Кристиан/ Kristiyan, Лъчезар/ Lachezar, Максим/Maksim, Петър/Petar, Самуил/Samuil, Светослав/ Svetoslav, Християн/ Hristiyan (3)

Table 5: List of Top 15 Masculine Given Names in Veliko Tarnovo, 2008-2018

In 2008 the following names were registered: *Кристиан/Kristian* (4th position, 6 references) and *Кристиян/Kristiyan* (8th position, 6 references) (variants of *Hristian/Христиан* and *Hristiyan/Християн*), *Константин/Konstantin* (8th position, 6 references, variant of *Костадин/Kostadin*), and *Теодор/Teodor* (9th position, 5 references, variant of *Тодор/Todor*).

In 2014, *Кристиян/Kristiyan* (7th position, 7 references) and *Теодор/Teodor* (8th position, 6 references) went up by one position.

In 2018 *Теодор/Teodor* (6th position, 11 references) continued to go up, while the more popular – according to the data from 2008, *Кристиан/Kristian* (12th position, 4 references) and *Кристиян/Kristiyan* (13th position, 3 references) fell in the list to the bottom of the table.

2. Feminine Given Names

Position	2008	2014	2018
1.	Александра/ Aleksandra (12)	<i>Никол/Nikol</i> (13)	<i>Никол/Nikol</i> (11)
2.	Виктория/Viktoriya, Габриела/Gabriela, Йоана/Yoana, <i>Никол/Nikol</i> (9)	Виктория/Viktoriya (11)	Михаела/ Mihaela (9)
3.	Наталия/Nataliya, Симона/Simona, Яна/Yana (7)	Габриела/Gabriela, Ивайла/Ivayla, Пламена/Plamena, Рая/Raya (7)	Габриела/ Gabriela, Йоана/Yoana, София/Sofiya (7)
4.	Даная/Danaya, <i>Теодора/Teodora</i> (6)	Сияна/Siyana (6)	Виктория/ Viktoriya, Дария/ Dariya, Рая/Raya (6)
5.	Ивелина/Ivelina, Магдалена/Magdalena, Мария/Mariya, Михаела/Mihaela, Рая/Raya, <i>Стефани/Stefani</i> (5)	Александра/Aleksandra, Ема/Ема, Изабел/Izabel, Преслава/Preslava, Христина/Hristina (5)	Ивайла/ Ivayla, Мария/ Mariya, Пламена/ Plamena, Симона/ Simona (5)
6.	Гергана/Gergana, Елена/Elena, Ивайла/Ivayla,	Дария/Dariya, Йоана/Yoana, Карина/Karina,	Александра/ Aleksandra, Ема/Ема,

	Калина/ <i>Kalina</i> , Карина/ <i>Karina</i> , Кристияна/ <i>Kristiyana</i> , Пламена/ <i>Plamena</i> , Преслава/ <i>Preslava</i> (4)	Катерина/ <i>Katerina</i> , Кристияна/ <i>Kristiyana</i> , Магдалена/ <i>Magdalena</i> , Мария/ <i>Mariya</i> (4)	Мирела/ <i>Mirela</i> , Християна/ <i>Hristiyana</i> (4)
7.	Анелия/ <i>Aneliya</i> , Биляна/ <i>Bilyana</i> , Бояна/ <i>Boyana</i> , Василена/ <i>Vasilena</i> , Десислава/ <i>Desislava</i> , Елица/ <i>Elitza</i> , Ема/ <i>Ema</i> , Емилия/ <i>Emiliya</i> , Камелия/ <i>Kameliya</i> , Мартина/ <i>Martina</i> , Моника/ <i>Monika</i> , Ния/ <i>Niya</i> (3)	Анастасия/ <i>Anastasiya</i> , Анна/ <i>Anna</i> , Дарина/ <i>Darina</i> , Деа/ <i>Dea</i> , Диана/ <i>Diana</i> , Емили/ <i>Emili</i> , Зорница/ <i>Zornitza</i> , Йоанна/ <i>Yoanna</i> , Кристина/ <i>Kristina</i> , Марая/ <i>Maraya</i> , Мартина/ <i>Martina</i> , Мая/ <i>Maya</i> , Моника/ <i>Monika</i> , Ния/ <i>Niya</i> Радина/ <i>Radina</i> , Сиана/ <i>Siana</i> (3)	Анна/ <i>Anna</i> , Ая/ <i>Aya</i> , Белослава/ <i>Beloslava</i> , Дея/ <i>Deya</i> , Емма/ <i>Emma</i> , Илина/ <i>Ilina</i> , Калина/ <i>Kalina</i> , Магдалена/ <i>Magdalena</i> , Мия/ <i>Miya</i> , Микаела/ <i>Mikaela</i> , Моника/ <i>Monika</i> , Тея/ <i>Teya</i> (3)

Table 6: List of Top 15 Feminine Given Names in Veliko Tarnovo, 2008-2018

In 2008 are observed such names as *Никол/Nikol* (2nd position, 9 references, variant of *Николета/Nikoleta*), *Теодора/Teodora* (4th position, 6 references, variant of *Тодора/Todora*), *Стефани/Stefani* (5th position, 5 references, variant of *Стефка/Stefka*), and *Кристияна/Kristiyana* (6th position, 4 references, variant of *Християна/Hristiyana*).

In 2014 the list includes *Никол/Nikol* (1st position, 13 references), *Кристияна/Kristiyana* (6th position, 4 references), *Емили/Emili* (variant of *Емилия/Emiliya*), *Марая/Maraya* (variant of *Мария/Mariya*), and *Кристина/Kristina* (variant of *Христина/Hristina*) all of them on the 7th position with 3 references.

In 2018 occurrences are diminished for *Никол/Nikol* (1st position, 11 references) and *Микаела/Mikaela* (7th position, 3 references, variant of *Михаела/Mihaela*).

V. Varna Given Name Data Analysis

In 2008, 4024 children (2097 boys and 1927 girls) were born in Varna. The number of the newly born in 2014 is 3486 (1832 boys and 1654 girls) (Chole-

va-Dimitrova, Vlahova-Angelova, Dancheva 2021: 60), while in 2018 it decreased to 3082 (1600 boys and 1482 girls).

1. Masculine Given Names

Position	2008	2014	2018
1.	Александър/ Aleksandar (102)	Александър/ Aleksandar (106)	Александър/ Aleksandar (75)
2.	Мартин/Martin (82)	Георги/Georgi, Мартин/Martin (84)	Мартин/Martin (59)
3.	Георги/Georgi (71)	Виктор/Viktor, Даниел/Daniel (78)	Виктор/Viktor, Даниел/Daniel, Теодор/Teodor (53)
4.	Виктор/Viktor (70)	Никола/Nikola (70)	Борис/Boris, Никола/Nikola (51)
5.	Никола/Nikola (57)	Калоян/Kaloyan (62)	Георги/Georgi (50)
6.	Даниел/Daniel (54)	Николай/Nikolay (59)	Калоян/Kaloyan (48)
7.	Николай/Nikolay (53)	Борис/Boris (55)	Симеон/Simeon (43)
8.	Борис/Boris (45)	Иван/Ivan (53)	Кристиян/ Kristiyan (40)
9.	Кристиян/ Kristiyan (41)	Димитър/Dimitar (49)	Димитър/Dimitar (36)
10.	Димитър/Dimitar, Калоян/Kaloyan (40)	Теодор/Teodor (47)	Самуил/Samuil (33)
11.	Максим/Maksim (37)	Кристиян/ Kristiyan (46)	Николай/Nikolay (32)
12.	Иван/Ivan (35)	Симеон/Simeon (36)	Борислав/Borislav (23)
13.	Теодор/Teodor (34)	Ивайло/Ivaylo (33)	Иван/Ivan, Филип/Filip (20)
14.	Стефан/Stefan (29)	Петър/Petar (28)	Павел/Pavel (18)
15.	Симеон/Simeon (27)	Михаил/Mihail (24)	Алекс/Aleks, Владимир/Vladimir,

			Йоан/Yoan (17)
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Table 7: List of Top 15 Masculine Given Names in Varna, 2008-2018

For 2008 the new male anthroponyms that represent new variants of traditional foreign proper nouns are: *Крестиян/Kristiyan* (9th position, 41 references, variant *Християн/Hristiyan*) and *Теодор/Teodor* (13th position, 34 references, variant of *Тодор/Todor*).

For 2014 the same onyms are observed but at different positions in the chart – *Теодор/Teodor* (10th position, 47 references), *Крестиян/Kristiyan* (11th position, 46 references). That phenomenon is noticed in the data for 2018 – *Теодор/Teodor* (3rd position, 53 references), *Крестиян/Kristiyan* (8th position, 40 references).

2. Feminine Given Names

Position	2008	2014	2018
1.	Виктория/ Viktoriya (75)	Виктория/Viktoriya (71)	София/Sofiya (42)
2.	Габриела/Gabriela (51)	<i>Никол/Nikol</i> (69)	Александра/ Aleksandra (39)
3.	Симона/Simona (47)	Габриела/Gabriela (50)	Виктория/ Viktoriya (36)
4.	Александра/Aleksandra (45)	Александра/ Aleksandra (45)	Габриела/ Gabriela, Симона/Simona (33)
5.	Йоана/Yoana (40)	Дария/Dariya (41)	Рая/Raya (29)
6.	Моника/Monika (31)	Рая/Raya (35)	Дария/Dariya, <i>Никол/Nikol</i> (25)
7.	Мария/Mariya (30)	Мария/Mariya (33)	Йоана/Yoana (22)
8.	<i>Никол/Nikol</i> , Рая/Raya (28)	Симона/Simona (30)	Михаела/ Mihaela (20)
9.	Калина/Kalina (22)	Йоана/Yoana, Магдалена/ Magdalena (26)	Карина/Karina (19)
10.	Елена/Elena (19)	Моника/Monika (25)	Ема/Ема, Ивайла/Ivayla

			(18)
11.	Гергана/ <i>Gergana</i> , Деница/ <i>Denitza</i> (18)	Ивайла/ <i>Ivayla</i> , Карина/ <i>Karina</i> (24)	Мария/ <i>Mariya</i> (17)
12.	Даная/ <i>Danaya</i> (17)	Елена/ <i>Elena</i> , Калина/ <i>Kalina</i> , София/ <i>Sofiya</i> (20)	Магдалена/ <i>Magdalena</i> , Моника/ <i>Monika</i> (16)
13.	София/ <i>Sofiya</i> (16)	Божидара/ <i>Bozhidara</i> , Ема/ <i>Ema</i> , Михаела/ <i>Mihaela</i> , Николета/ <i>Nikoleta</i> , Сияна/ <i>Siyana</i> (17)	Вероника/ <i>Veronika</i> , Мая/ <i>Maya</i> , Пламена/ <i>Plamena</i> (15)
14.	Ема/ <i>Ema</i> , <i>Кристина/Kristina</i> , Михаела/ <i>Mihaela</i> , Ралица/ <i>Ralitza</i> , <i>Теодора/Teodora</i> (15)	<i>Крисия/Krisiya</i> , <i>Кристина/Kristina</i> , Марина/ <i>Marina</i> , Ния/ <i>Niya</i> , Полина/ <i>Polina</i> (16)	Вяра/ <i>Vyara</i> (14)
15.	Карина/ <i>Karina</i> (14)	Гергана/ <i>Gergana</i> , Ева/ <i>Eva</i> , Елица/ <i>Elitza</i> , Мартина/ <i>Martina</i> (15)	Божидара/ <i>Bozhidara</i> , Елена/ <i>Elena</i> , Калина/ <i>Kalina</i> , <i>Теодора/Teodora</i> (13)

Table 8: List of Top 15 Feminine Given Names in Varna, 2008-2018

In 2008 in the list of the new variants of traditional foreign feminine given names are found *Никол/Nikol* (8th position, 28 references, variant of *Николема/Nikoleta*), *Теодора/Teodora* (variant of *Тодора/Todora*) and *Кристина/Kristina* (variant of *Христина/Hristina*) both on 14th position with 15 references.

In 2014 *Теодора/Teodora* is missing while the other two change their positions – *Никол/Nikol* (2nd position, 69 references), *Кристина/Kristina* (14th position, 14 references).

In 2018 *Теодора/Teodora* (15th position, 13 references) appears again, while *Кристина/Kristina* is dropped. *Никол/Nikol* (6th position, 25 references) loses popularity.

VI. Conclusions

As it was mentioned in the initial part of the article, the data includes the most preferred 15 given names in the biggest settlements in the Northern

part of Bulgaria and the new variants of traditional foreign given names are in the focus of interest.

Each settlement may be described in short with the features it possesses – Veliko Tarnovo used to be the capital of the country and is situated in the middle of the country, close to Pleven, Ruse is on the Danube bank, Varna is on the seaside. All the four towns are big tourist, university and cultural centers.

It is surprising that the researched anthroponyms are less in number in Varna, that is a bigger settlement, if compared with the other three, where an important international port and airport are situated, so the influence of foreign cultures is stronger than in Veliko Tarnovo and Pleven, for instance, where traditions are supposed to be more solid.

The given names included in the researched lists are under the influence of the most popular names for boys and girls in Bulgaria. All of them are in accordance with the religious traditions in the country – the majority of them are names of saints worshiped by the Orthodox Church. Feminine variants are more numerous and various than the masculine ones.

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